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A critical systematic review of the Neurotracker perceptual-cognitive training tool

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26 Abstract:

27 In this systematic review, we evaluate the scientific evidence behind “Neurotracker”, one of the
28 most popular perceptual-cognitive training tools in sports. The tool, which is also used in
29 rehabilitation and ageing research to examine cognitive abilities, uses a 3D multiple object tracking
30 (MOT) task. In this review, we examine Neurotracker from both a sport science and a basic science
31 perspective. We first summarize the sport science debate regarding the value of general cognitive
32 skill training, based on tools such as Neurotracker, versus sport-specific skill training. We then
33 consider the several hundred MOT publications in cognitive and vision science from the last thirty
34 years that have investigated cognitive functions and object tracking processes. This literature
35 suggests that the abilities underlying object tracking are not those advertised by the Neurotracker
36 manufacturers. With a systematic literature search, we scrutinize the evidence for whether general
37 cognitive skills can be tested and trained with Neurotracker and whether these trained skills transfer
38 to other domains. The literature has major limitations, for example a total absence of preregistered
39 studies, which makes the evidence for improvements for working memory and sustained attention
40 very weak. For other skills as well, the effects are mixed. Only three studies investigated far transfer
41 to ecologically valid tasks, two of which did not find any effect. We provide recommendations for
42 future Neurotracker research to improve the evidence base and for making better use of sport and
43 basic science findings.

44

45 Keywords: sport, transfer, vision, attention, intervention

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76 **Introduction**

77 The primary goal of most types of sports training is to have positive transfer of training to
78 competition. That is, improved performance on game day. Such training includes strength and
79 endurance training, skill training, and perceptual and decision-making training. For the latter,
80 improving perceptual-cognitive skills, (i.e., processing the most important information at the right
81 time to make accurate decisions) likely separates novices from experts (Mann et al., 2007). In this
82 systematic review, we will combine research from sports science and basic science to evaluate one of
83 the most popular perceptual-cognitive training tools in sport, called “Neurotracker”.

84 **Perceptual-Cognitive Skill Training: Specific or General?**

85 Currently, there are two distinct approaches to improve perceptual-cognitive skills. In the first,
86 led mainly by sport scientists, it has been proposed that training should be highly context- and
87 sports-specific. That is, to be effective in improving performance during the actual sport, the training
88 must contain the perceptual information (e.g., spacing between opponents, expansion of a ball) that
89 is present in the actual game (Baker et al., 2003a, 2003b; Broadbent et al., 2015; Williams et al.,
90 2011). This approach dates to Brunswick’s (1956) concept of representative design which demands
91 representative tasks in perceptual-cognitive skills training that replicate the real world as closely as
92 possible in terms of a few key components (specifically, perception–action coupling, action fidelity,
93 and perceptual information) to improve the transfer of learning (for a discussion see Broadbent et
94 al., 2015, p. 329).

95 In the alternative approach, it is proposed that general perceptual and cognitive processes can
96 be trained out of context (e.g., using stimuli and tools from ophthalmology). This type of training is
97 sometimes called brain training, perceptual training, attention training, or mind training (Harris et al.,
98 2018). On occasion, the producers of the associated products have made claims that go beyond that
99 warranted by the evidence. The manufacturers of the Lumosity software, for example, were fined in

100 2016 for “deceptive advertising” because they suggested that training generic vision and attention
101 skills would help against “memory loss, dementia, and even Alzheimer’s disease”
102 ([https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/press-releases/2016/01/lumosity-pay-2-million-settle-ftc-](https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/press-releases/2016/01/lumosity-pay-2-million-settle-ftc-deceptive-advertising-charges)
103 [deceptive-advertising-charges](https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/press-releases/2016/01/lumosity-pay-2-million-settle-ftc-deceptive-advertising-charges), received on 10 August 2020). Recently, Simons et al. (2016) raised
104 serious concerns even about more modest claims for the benefits of brain training programs after
105 finding low methodological rigor in the studies purporting to show their effectiveness.

106 A growing body of non-sport-specific vision and attention training techniques are used in the
107 hope that they will improve visual-motor skills in sports (for reviews see Appelbaum & Erickson,
108 2018; Hadlow et al., 2018; Harris et al., 2018). The range of training tools spans basic visual abilities
109 such as depth perception and peripheral vision, visual-motor training for eye-hand coordination and
110 other skills, and perceptual-cognitive training for information processing and decision making (for a
111 review see Appelbaum & Erickson, 2018).

112 How effective is such general training at improving sport-specific skills? Some recent topical
113 reviews have assessed portions of the existing evidence. Transfer from one task to another has been
114 classified based on amount of difference between tasks (Schmidt et al., 2019) into near transfer (to
115 similar tasks), mid-level transfer (to tasks of a similar cognitive domain), and far transfer (to real-life
116 tasks; Harris et al., 2018; Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020). Critically, for sports training, the
117 intention in using a perceptual-cognitive training tool is for it to provide far-transfer effects to
118 improve sport-specific skills on the field. While some are optimistic that such training can transfer to
119 improved performance in competition i.e., “far transfer” (e.g., Wilkins & Appelbaum, 2019), others
120 are skeptical, arguing that such training is only likely to lead to “near transfer” in the form of
121 improvement on the training task itself (Appelbaum & Erickson, 2018; Gray, 2020; Hadlow et al.,
122 2018; Harris et al., 2018; Renshaw et al., 2019).

123 One of the most popular and well-studied generalized perceptual-cognitive training tools is
124 Neurotracker. Its producers claim that training with it yields benefits that include far transfer. Their
125 home page (<https://neurotracker.net/performance/>, retrieved 10 May 2020) includes the following

126 phrases that indicate the claims they make for the benefits of Neurotracker training: “focusing on key
127 play opportunities”, “filter out incoming sensory distractions”, “stay sharp under high-pressure
128 demands”, “see more opportunities in any situation”, “interpret body language more effectively”,
129 “perceptively slow down the environment”, “respond more quickly and efficiently”, “improve your
130 response accuracy”, and “avoid overly impulsive actions”. Many of these correspond to far transfer
131 effects, given that the Neurotracker task is restricted to paying attention to moving spheres on a
132 computer display. In this systematic review, we aim to identify what the evidence indicates about the
133 benefits of Neurotracker.

134 **Neurotracker**

135 Neurotracker is promoted and sold by the Faubert Applied Research Centre with links to the
136 School of Optometry of the University of Montréal, as well as CogniSens Athletics Inc. Professional
137 sports clubs in the NFL, NBA, NHL, and EPL have been reported to use the Neurotracker, as has the
138 U.S. military ([https://neurotracker.net/2019/11/27/qa-with-scott-kozak-on-innovations-in-military-
139 training/](https://neurotracker.net/2019/11/27/qa-with-scott-kozak-on-innovations-in-military-training/)). Neurotracker is a 3D multiple object tracking (MOT) task that requires one to fixate on a
140 green dot in the middle of the screen and use peripheral vision to monitor the movements of eight
141 yellow spheres. Each trial consists of four phases, as described by Parsons et al. (2014, p. 4): “During
142 the first phase of each trial, all 8 spheres appear in yellow and are stationary. Next, the 4 target
143 spheres that the trainee must track appear in red for 2 seconds, before switching back to yellow. The
144 spheres begin movement and tracking then occurs over a period of 8 seconds. All 8 spheres move
145 along a linear path through the cube; should any sphere encounter an obstacle it bounces off that
146 obstacle and continues along its new path. At the end of this phase, each sphere is identified with a
147 number and the trainee is asked to verbally state their responses”.

148 One of the earliest published papers on Neurotracker (Parsons et al., 2014) provides hypotheses
149 regarding potential training and transfer effects, which are frequently cited by Neurotracker
150 proponents. In particular, Parsons et al. (2014, p. 2) claim that the “[...] cognitive enhancer [i.e.,
151 Neurotracker] has four defining characteristics”, although only three are subsequently listed: 1) MOT,

152 2) large visual field, 3) a binocular 3D display. The Neurotracker, Parsons et al. (2014) state, is based
 153 on two principles: “isolation” and “overloading”. Isolation means “that a number of functions
 154 solicited for the task should be limited and consistent. A training task should not draw on a random
 155 and inconsistent combination of cognitive functions to complete. If isolation does not occur, training
 156 effects are reduced... Overloading a function means soliciting it beyond its current ability. To properly
 157 train any function, overloading must occur so that adaptation (in the brain: neuroplasticity) can take
 158 place.” (Parsons et al., 2014, p. 2). Overloading is achieved by adjusting the speed of every trial to
 159 ensure the task is sufficiently difficult.

160 Parsons et al. (2014) and the Neurotracker website (<https://neurotracker.net/benefits/>,
 161 retrieved 10 May) both state that training with the Neurotracker improves several cognitive
 162 functions: attention (sustained, selective, divided, inhibition), short-term memory, working memory
 163 and information processing speed (see Table 1). Besides these benefits, Neurotracker is also said to
 164 improve “awareness” (e.g., peripheral vision) and decision-making
 165 (<https://neurotracker.net/performance/>, retrieved 10 May). The justification for these claims is not
 166 always clear.

167 To evaluate the possible benefits of Neurotracker training, this paper will first review work on
 168 multiple object tracking generally that has probed its component processes. This first set of work did
 169 not investigate the effects of training, but rather used the tools of psychophysics and the
 170 experimental study of visual attention to uncover the underlying perceptual, attentional, and
 171 cognitive processes involved.

172 **Table 1**

173 *Abilities claimed to be improved by Neurotracker training according to the Neurotracker website.*

Cognitive Function	Definition
Attention	
Sustained	The ability to maintain selective attention over time
Selective	The ability to attend to/focus on/cognitively process a given thing
Divided	The ability to selectively attend to multiple loci at once (multifocal)
Inhibition	The ability to not attend/focus on/cognitively process a given thing
Short-term memory	The ability to retain information over a short time span (20-30 s)

Working memory	The ability to retain and transform information over a short time span
Processing speed	The time needed to consciously integrate perceptual stimuli

174 Note. Source: <https://neurotracker.net/benefits/> (retrieved 10 May); Table adapted from Parsons et al.,
 175 2014 who used the definitions from the third edition of the book "Cognitive Neuroscience" by Banich and
 176 Compton, 2011).

177 **MOT Research and Cognitive Functions**

178 The first formal study of multiple object tracking was conducted by Pylyshyn and Storm (1988).
 179 Participants kept their eyes on a square at the center of the screen (with fixation monitored by an
 180 eye-tracker) while attempting to keep track of 1 to 5 moving crosses, among a total of 10 crosses
 181 moving along random paths for 7 to 15s. Additionally, they indicated (with a key-press) when any of
 182 the target crosses was flashed. If a distractor, i.e., one of the objects that did not need to be tracked,
 183 was flashed, the participants were not to respond. Relatively few flash response errors were made
 184 (2% for 1 target, 14% for 5 targets), showing that participants were able to track up to 5 out of 10
 185 randomly-moving objects with high accuracy.

186 Over the following 30 years, more than 160 peer-reviewed MOT journal articles have been
 187 published (Meyerhoff et al., 2017). In their tutorial review, Meyerhoff et al. (2017) explain that it is
 188 still unclear whether MOT is a singular process or instead "[...] consists of several subroutines
 189 (including attentional selection and working memory processes) that interact with each other based
 190 on current task demands" (Meyerhoff et al., 2017, p. 1269). That sentence of Meyerhoff et al. (2017)
 191 underscores how much remains unknown about MOT and immediately questions the claim that
 192 several abilities are improved by using Neurotracker. However, the basic science of MOT does
 193 provide some strong suggestions regarding what processes are involved in Neurotracker task
 194 performance.

195 *Sustained Attention*

196 The Neurotracker website claims that the Neurotracker trains sustained attention, and Parsons
 197 et al. (2014, p. 9) specifically argue that 3D-MOT "trains the ability to dynamically shift attention
 198 along multiple foci". However, the authors use this same phrase to define "divided attention" (see
 199 "divided attention" section below). In the basic MOT literature, whether or not MOT results in

200 dynamic shifting of attention among the tracked targets has been an active debate since the very
201 first MOT publication, which claimed to rule out shifting of attention (Pylyshyn & Storm, 1988). Some
202 later researchers argued that each object receives its own “spotlight” that works in parallel
203 (sometimes termed multifocal attention, Cavanagh & Alvarez, 2005). More recent evidence,
204 however, seems to indicate that a serial, potentially oscillatory, process imposes the limit on number
205 of targets that can be tracked and maximum tracking speed (Holcombe & Chen, 2013), consistent
206 with recent hybrid models of MOT that involve both parallel and serial processing (Li et al., 2019;
207 Lovett et al., 2019). If these latter theories are correct, then the Neurotracker task should indeed
208 involve the dynamic shift of attention, as claimed, although whether training improves this ability is a
209 separate question.

210 Accurate performance in the Neurotracker task appears to be limited primarily by how many
211 targets a person can track, and at what speed. MOT research has shown that these two factors,
212 number of targets and maximum speed at which they can be tracked, directly trade off – a person
213 can track a large number of objects moving at a slow speed but only a few objects moving at high
214 speed. If the objects move quickly enough, a person can only track one (Alvarez & Franconeri, 2007;
215 Holcombe & Chen, 2012, 2013). This points to an attentional resource that can be divided among
216 moving objects, and the more attention is divided, the slower a target can be tracked.

217 A component of attention that limits both number of targets and maximum target speed is,
218 quite surprisingly, specific to each visual hemifield (everything to the left of the point of gaze is the
219 left hemifield, and everything to the right is the right hemifield). That is, if there are enough moving
220 targets confined to one visual hemifield (say, the left one) at a high enough speed that adding an
221 additional target will substantially degrade performance, that degradation does *not* happen if a
222 target is added to the other hemifield (Alvarez & Cavanagh, 2005; Holcombe & Chen, 2012, 2013). If
223 Neurotracker performance is limited by the hemifield-specific resource, it is less likely that the
224 Neurotracker overloads working memory and short-term memory, as they are **not** hemifield-specific
225 (Alvarez et al., 2012).

226 Sustained attention is expected to be “overloaded” by having objects move in three (3D) rather
227 than two dimensions (2D), because higher speed thresholds can be achieved in 3D (Faubert &
228 Sidebottom, 2012). This expectation is based on the results reported in an abstract to a vision
229 conference (Tinjust et al., 2010). Other MOT studies, however, show the opposite effect: Tracking
230 objects on different depth planes – as in 3D – has been found to be easier than tracking objects on
231 one depth plane – as in 2D (see Cooke et al., 2017; Dünser & Mancero, 2009; Viswanathan &
232 Mingolla, 2002). Similar to 2D MOT, tracking accuracy is impaired in 3D when object speed is
233 increased or when distances between objects are reduced (Cooke et al., 2017; Ur Rehman et al.,
234 2015). Sustained attention involves parallel and serial tracking processes that are sensitive to the
235 number and speed of objects, the distance between objects as well as their location in the visual 3D
236 environment.

237 *Selective Attention*

238 In the context of MOT, selective attention is the ability to focus on targets rather than
239 distractors and it is expected that higher object speeds and shorter distances between targets and
240 distractors increase selective attention demands (Parsons et al., 2014, p. 9). At the beginning of an
241 MOT task, such as Neurotracker, featural attention (to red, in the case of Neurotracker) is used to
242 select the target objects. Selective attention must then be sustained on these objects when they
243 become identical to the distractors, and then tracked as they move. For neurotypical individuals the
244 initial selection process does not appear to be demanding (Drew & Vogel, 2008) – the average
245 capacity limit for selection is higher than that of tracking (Alvarez & Franconeri, 2007). When the
246 number of objects to track is low and their speed slow, participants can track objects for at least ten
247 minutes with little loss (Wolfe et al., 2007). Thus, while many potential athlete users may imagine
248 that a test of attention tests how *long* they can pay attention, this is not likely to be the reason for
249 differences among people on MOT performance. With featural attention (e.g., attention to color)
250 needed for target acquisition unlikely to be taxed in typical people by Neurotracker, and only needed
251 briefly, featural attention seems unlikely to improve with Neurotracker training.

252 Selective attention is also affected by short-range perceptual interference among targets and
253 distractors (often called “crowding”) when a target gets too close to a distractor (Holcombe et al.,
254 2014; Vater et al., 2017b). There are large individual differences in crowding that correlate with other
255 visual tasks such as spatial localization (Greenwood et al., 2017) and reading (Pelli & Tillman, 2008).
256 Moreover, training on action video games may reduce crowding and improve reading in
257 developmental dyslexia (Bertoni et al., 2019). This raises the possibility that any benefits from MOT
258 training may be due in part, or even in whole, to a reduction in short-range perceptual interference.

259 For tasks in which participants do not need to keep their gaze fixed on a single location, overt
260 selective attention in MOT can be examined by using eye-tracking devices. The associated studies
261 have found that MOT task participants look some of the time at individual targets, and some of the
262 time at points near the targets’ centroid (i.e., looking at the center of mass between the targets
263 using peripheral vision), even if nothing is there (Fehd & Seiffert, 2008; Lukavský, 2013; Vater et al.,
264 2016, 2017a). Keeping the gaze near the centroid minimizes the average distance into peripheral
265 vision of the targets, which can greatly improve perception of the targets. The proportion of centroid
266 vs. target looking depends on the number of targets (Zelinsky & Neider, 2008) and the distance
267 between objects (Vater et al., 2017b; Zelinsky & Todor, 2010). Gaze direction frequently switches
268 among targets (Elfanagely et al., 2011) and is rarely directed at distractors (Fehd & Seiffert, 2010;
269 Lukavský, 2013; Vater et al., 2016, 2017a). When a particular pattern of object trajectories are shown
270 to participants a second time, the gaze pattern tends to be very similar to the first time (Lukavský,
271 2013). Requiring that participants move their gaze in a specific way impairs tracking performance
272 (Fehd & Seiffert, 2010). It is possible that substantial improvements in performance as a result of
273 MOT training arise from improvements in how selective attention and the eyes are moved, but this
274 does not appear to have been explored.

275 *Divided Attention*

276 Divided attention is described as the “ability to dynamically shift attention along multiple loci”
277 (Parsons et al., 2014, p. 9), which is exactly the same phrase that the same authors used to describe

278 sustained attention (see section above on “Sustained Attention”). Another reason the Parsons et al.
279 (2014) definition is inappropriate is that attention to multiple loci may involve simultaneous
280 allocation to multiple loci rather than dynamic shifting (Awh & Pashler, 2000; Pylyshyn & Storm,
281 1988). In the study the authors referred to when explaining divided attention (Spelke et al., 1976), a
282 dual-task paradigm – with a reading and writing task – was used. Consequently, one can be sure one
283 is studying divided attention with Neurotracker only when it is combined with a secondary task.
284 Otherwise, divided attention cannot be distinguished from selective attention.

285 One paper on MOT and secondary tasks found that tracking performance is impaired if the
286 secondary task is conversing on the phone, but not if it is a listening task (Kunar et al., 2008). Tracking
287 performance is also impaired when the secondary task is visual change detection (Vater et al.,
288 2017a). These results suggest that visual secondary tasks might impair tracking performance but
289 some auditory secondary tasks may not.

290 *Inhibition*

291 According to Parsons et al. (2014, p. 9), inhibition is a process underlying Neurotracker
292 performance and it is “[...] the ability to not focus on non-pertinent information”, which in MOT
293 requires that one “inhibit focus from distractors”. Evidence that distractor inhibition occurs in MOT
294 was found by Pylyshyn (2006) with a probe detection task. Suppression effects depend on the
295 similarity between targets and distractors in their motion and form (Feria, 2012) and depth (Pylyshyn
296 et al., 2008). Relevant to 3D MOT tasks such as Neurotracker, non-targets on a different depth plane
297 have been found to be filtered out *without* the use of inhibition (Pylyshyn et al., 2008). Nevertheless,
298 distractor locations and changes are often perceived (Alvarez & Oliva, 2008; Vater, 2019) and
299 distractor displacements impair tracking performance (Meyerhoff et al., 2015). All of these results
300 indicate that distractor locations are still encoded.

301 *Short Term and Working Memory*

302 Short-term memory as trained by the Neurotracker according to Parsons et al. (2014, p. 9) is
303 described as “the ability to temporarily retain a limited amount of information in consciousness” and
304 working memory as “the ability to manipulate information stored in a temporary bank to suit the
305 task at hand”. These definitions are consistent with large parts of the memory literature (Cowan,
306 2017).

307 Parsons et al. (2014) provided no evidence that the Neurotracker trains short-term memory, and
308 in MOT research more broadly, the nature of the link between MOT and memory (short-term or
309 working) is still debated. Studies have found that a concurrent working memory task impairs MOT
310 performance (Fougnie & Marois, 2006, 2009), suggesting processes in common, but this interference
311 may be restricted to spatial memory (Zhang et al., 2010). Potentially, then, spatial memory may be
312 taxed by Neurotracker training. An individual-difference study also found an association between
313 spatial working memory and MOT performance (Wilmer et al., 2016).

314 *Information Processing Speed*

315 Information processing speed is defined by Parsons et al. (2014, p. 9) first as “The time needed
316 to consciously integrate perceptual stimuli” but later as the speed at which visual stimuli enter
317 “bottom-up” through “sensory organs to primary processing areas and then through higher order
318 processing or ‘association’ areas” (p.9). Aside from Neurotracker papers, we did not find any MOT
319 studies purporting to investigate the role of this construct in MOT performance. Parsons et al. (2014)
320 claim that the target speed thresholds measured by Neurotracker “directly evoke visual information
321 processing speed capacities” (p.9). However, the basis for this claim is obscure. Rather than MOT /
322 Neurotracker performance being limited by the speed at which sensory information reaches a
323 particular area of cortex, it may be wholly constrained by other processes, including crowding or the
324 rate at which attention moves or switches among multiple stimuli (Holcombe et al., 2014; Lovett et
325 al., 2019).

326 Moreover, while Parsons et al. (2014) define information processing speed as having to do with
327 the speed of sensory processing, the tasks they used to assess information processing speed are
328 characterized in the neuropsychology literature as measuring “the efficiency of cognitive function”. It
329 is assessed using timed tests that typically challenge relatively simple cognitive operations (Sweet,
330 2011). Specifically, the tasks used by Parsons et al. (2014) were subtests of the Wechsler Adult
331 Intelligence Scale, the Integrated Visual and Auditory Continuous Performance Test, and the Delis-
332 Kaplan Executive Functions System Color-Word Interference Test. Performance on these tests may
333 be constrained more by the effectiveness and error-proneness of more cognitive operations than by
334 faster sensory processing (Sweet, 2011).

335 *How MOT Performance Correlates With Performance in Other Cognitive Tasks*

336 Studies of individual differences measure the extent to which those who score highly on one
337 task also score highly on other tasks. The results provide an indication of whether the processes that
338 produce variation in tracking performance also produce variation in other specific tasks. Only one
339 published paper, by Huang et al. (2012), tested a substantial number of individuals both on MOT and
340 multiple other attention-involving tasks. Huang et al. (2012) tested approximately 250 people and
341 found that MOT performance correlated highly with several simple tasks requiring judgments about
342 briefly-presented visual stimuli. All the tests other than MOT used static rather than moving objects.
343 Positive correlations of between 0.5 and 0.7 with MOT performance were found for visual search for
344 conjunctions, visual search for spatial configurations, counting the number of items in a brief display,
345 identification of a briefly-presented post-masked color, symmetry detection, time to make a
346 response to the color of a stimulus, visual short-term memory, and change detection. Much weaker
347 correlations were found between MOT performance and Raven’s test of intelligence (0.27) and also
348 several tasks thought to test suppression or avoidance of interference, such as the Stroop task (0.20),
349 attentional capture (0.02), and inhibition of return (0.08). The findings indicate that only some
350 attention-related tasks cluster together in the variation among individuals, but the full pattern is far
351 from clear.

352 *Summary.* As can be seen from this review of related MOT research from the last 30 years, it is
353 still debated how the attentional skills, that are claimed to be improved with Neurotracker training,
354 are involved when tracking multiple objects. Whether these skills can be trained with MOT had not
355 been tested when Parsons et al. (2014) made their claims.

356 **Aims and Focus of This Systematic Review**

357 Since 2014, a number of studies have investigated possible benefits of Neurotracker training.
358 With this systematic review, we aim to provide those using or considering using the Neurotracker
359 with preliminary answers to two questions:

360 1) Does Neurotracker test and train the cognitive skills that its makers suggest?

361 2) Do the skills trained transfer to other domains?

362 To answer these questions, we first evaluate all scientific references provided by the
363 manufacturer and search for additional peer-reviewed journal articles that were not cited. After the
364 search, we discuss the scientific evidence for near or far transfer effects from Neurotracker training
365 studies in different populations and specifically identify cognitive or motor skills that can (or cannot)
366 be improved. Finally, we make suggestions for future research and for practitioners interested in
367 perceptual-cognitive skill training.

368 **Methods**

369 Major problems for assessing the strength of evidence for claims in psychology include
370 publication bias, researcher degrees of freedom such as not committing to a particular sample size
371 before beginning running participants, and other questionable research practices such as p-hacking.
372 The phenomenon of publication bias is that researchers only tend to publish a study if it favors their
373 hypothesis. This means that effects on average turn out to be much smaller when unpublished
374 studies are included (Ferguson & Brannick, 2012). We contacted Faubert (a co-author on almost
375 every published Neurotracker study) in June 2020 and January 2021 and asked if he knew of any

376 unpublished studies, but we have not received a response. Therefore, we only include studies listed
377 on the webpage or identified by our literature search.

378 Our literature search consisted of both a search and analysis of the references provided on the
379 webpage (www.neurotracker.net), and also a systematic literature search where we followed the
380 four steps of the *Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses* (PRISMA)
381 statement (Moher et al., 2009): identification, screening, eligibility inspection and inclusion of
382 relevant papers. After the identification stage, the reference lists from both the webpage and the
383 search were combined and checked for duplicates before continuing with the subsequent PRISMA
384 steps of screening, eligibility inspection and inclusion.

385 Identification of Studies

386 The Neurotracker webpages link to a document with 35 summaries of studies completed
387 (https://drive.google.com/file/d/11opgnL6IRmnlkW-pNmhqdB_6BZpLp52O/view, retrieved 10 May).
388 On the first pages of the document, each reference is linked to a slide, where the aims, methods and
389 findings of the research are summarized. In some cases, illustrations of the study or results are
390 displayed on the slides too. Two of the 35 research items are linked to the same slide (study #18 and
391 #19 and #27 and #30), so it appears the list actually consists of only 33 research items. A web-link to
392 each research item is included, allowing us to classify items as “peer-reviewed journal articles”,
393 “journal articles without peer-review”, “preprints”, “conference abstracts” and “other”. An additional
394 Google Scholar search using the title of each item was conducted to check whether the research was
395 published elsewhere. If a research item was presented at a conference or listed as a preprint, but
396 was eventually published in a journal, the reference is here listed as “journal article”. The list of
397 references is likely complete, or nearly complete, as the latest was published on 17 April 2020
398 (Lysenko-Martin et al., 2020).

399 In a second identification step, we conducted a systematic literature search in May 2020 using
400 the Scopus, ScienceDirect, Web of Knowledge, and Pubmed databases. The searches were conducted

401 by two raters, the first author and a trained student assistant, working independently. In each
 402 database, we searched for the word “Neurotracker” in “all fields” and limited the results to English
 403 and to the type “article”. Any conference abstracts, dissertations, book chapters, and reviews were
 404 thereby excluded. The results were exported as .ris, .bib or .nbib-files and imported into the citation
 405 software [®]citavi (2018; version 6). With this procedure, we identified 50 articles (Figure 1).

406

407

408 **Figure 1. PRISMA scheme for the identification, screening, eligibility and inclusion stages.**

409 **Screening, Eligibility and Inclusion**

410 After combining the references of both searches, 84 research items were searched for
411 duplicates, and using the built-in function of citavi, the 28 duplicates were removed. Next, we
412 continued with screening to limit the set to articles published in peer-reviewed journals. We
413 excluded articles that were not published in a peer-reviewed journal (3), as well as conference
414 abstracts (7), preprints (1), articles that were not in English (5), and articles with no available full text
415 (1). After removing these 17 research items, 39 full texts remained. We excluded 10 studies that did
416 not use the Neurotracker in their experiments. These papers mainly cited a paper with
417 “Neurotracker” in the title, so that the search criterion was only found in the reference list. In the
418 end, 29 papers could be included in this systematic review.

419 **Data Extraction and Analyses**

420 The information extracted from each article followed criteria similar to those of Simons et al.
421 (2016)¹, adapted for the current review (see Table 2). With this extracted information, we first
422 provide an overview of experimental designs and findings of all the studies.

423 In the next step, we evaluate the intervention studies for possible transfer effects. To do this, we
424 check whether the Neurotracker was used for measurement (M), to assess learning effects (i.e.,
425 improved Neurotracker performance with practice) (L), and whether a study investigated transfer
426 effects (T) to another task. This trichotomy was used by the manufacturer for their list of references.

427 Similar to previous reviews (Harris et al., 2018; Simons et al., 2016), we distinguish between
428 near transfer effects (to a similar task) and far transfer effects (to a real-life task). In the summary
429 table (Table 5), we use colors to indicate whether transfer tests yielded positive results (green),
430 positive but with methodological concerns (yellow) or no effect (red). The evaluation of the methods

¹<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1tdEChpYHH1nnTc2Chqow0FY7Rj70jHrbLI5OhOPmQbE/edit#gid=0>

431 is based on criteria proposed by Simons et al. (2016) and described in more detail in our section
 432 “Intervention studies and transfer effects”.

433 **Table 2**

434 *Information extracted from each study.*

Category	Sub-category	Definition or example
Study Information	Source	Reference from homepage or literature search
	Title	Article title
	Authors	List of authors
	Year	Year of publication
	Journal	Journal name
	Peer-reviewed	Yes/no indicating whether the journal includes peer review
	Design	Experimental intervention, correlation assessed, between-group comparison, technical report, theoretical report
Intervention group	N training	Number of participants in the training group
	Participant type	Researched population
	Age group	Mean or range of age of participants
	Intervention interval	Number of training/test sessions (and distribution over time)
	Total training time	Amount of minutes (estimated based on number of sessions)
	Training task	Task used in intervention group
Control group	N control	Number of participants in the control group
	Type of control	None, active, passive, placebo
	Matched control	Criteria on which participants were matched between groups
	Participant type	Researched population
	Age group	Mean or range of age of participants
	Control interval	Number of training/test sessions (and distribution over time)
	Total training time	Total minutes (estimated based on number of sessions)
Methods	Nr. Targets	Number of MOT targets
	Nr. Distractors	Number of MOT Distractors
	Outcome task	Task with main dependent variable
	Additional tasks	Other tasks with dependent (or control) variables
Results	Measurement*	Indicates if Neurotracker was used for measurement
	Learning*	Indicates if participants improved Neurotracker performance
	Transfer*	Indicates if Neurotracker training improved other skills
	Near transfer	Indicates improvements in a similar task
	Far transfer	Indicates improvements in a real-world task
Trained skills	Attention*	Improvements in selective attention, divided attention, sustained attention, or short-term memory
	Awareness*	Improvements in perception
	Decision-making*	Improvements in decision-making
	Executive function*	Improvements in inhibition, shifting, or switching
	Working memory*	Improvements in working memory
	Processing speed*	Improvements in processing speed

435 *Note.* The symbol “*” indicates items that are included in the overview of references on the Neurotracker
 436 webpage.

437

438 **Review and Discussion**

439 On the webpage “Neurotracker.net”, 33 research outputs are provided as scientific references.
440 These references consist of 21 peer-reviewed articles, three articles published in journals with no
441 peer-review, one preprint, seven conference abstracts and two items that could not be found after
442 the additional online search. From the 21 peer-reviewed articles, one was published in Spanish
443 language (Junyent et al., 2015) and was therefore excluded. With our literature search, nine
444 additional articles could be identified that used Neurotracker, but the full text of one study was not
445 available (Varanoske et al., 2020). Thus, our evaluation was based on 29 published studies (see Table
446 3).

447 Since 2012, articles using Neurotracker have been published in internationally well-known
448 journals such as *Scientific Reports*, *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, *Intelligence*, and *Frontiers in*
449 *Psychology*, while others were published in less well-known journals, such as the Brazilian journal
450 “*Dementia & Neuropsychologia*” and “*Ageing Science & Mental Health Studies*” on the Research
451 Open platform. The three most cited articles on Google Scholar and Scopus (date of search: 5 May
452 2020) are:

453 1) Faubert (2013, Scholar: 162 citations; Scopus: 78 citations): This study compared professional
454 athletes, elite amateurs, and non-athletes on Neurotracker learning rates.

455 2) Faubert and Sidebottom (2012, Scholar: 145 citations; Scopus: 60 citations): a theoretical
456 article discussing the potential benefits of Neurotracker training.

457 3) Romeas et al. (2016, Scholar: 130 citations; Scopus: 63 citations): an intervention study that
458 claims that Neurotracker training improves decision-making for passes in soccer.

459 In terms of the study designs, the included studies consist of 17 intervention studies (i.e. studies
460 that used Neurotracker as a training tool for more than one training session), all of which used the
461 Neurotracker as the intervention, except Fragala et al. (2014) which used a resistance-training
462 intervention and Neurotracker to measure performance in the pre- and posttest; we report the

463 findings of that study only in the Neurotracker non-intervention study section in the supplement
464 section. The remaining sixteen comprise five correlational studies, three within-between-group
465 comparisons, two between-group comparisons, one within-group comparison, one study with a
466 combination of a between-group comparison (Experiment 1) and an intervention (Experiment 2) and
467 one theoretical paper (the Faubert & Sidebottom paper).

468 In the following, to assess the most important issue of whether there are near or far transfer
469 effects, we will focus on the intervention studies. The other sorts of research designs in this literature
470 typically do not provide good evidence for causal effects of training (Shadish et al., 2002, p. 484) –
471 while quasi-experiments may provide good evidence, this literature contains only simpler
472 observational studies. To provide a complete overview of the literature, however, we also summarize
473 the non-intervention studies in the Supplement section.

474

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475 **Table 3**476 *Included studies with first author, year of publication, study design, any outcomes other than Neurotracker performance, and the main claimed findings.*

First author	Year	Design	Additional tests	Main claimed finding(s)
Assed	2016	intervention	Memo Checkup	Neurotracker training led to improvements in episodic and working memory, faster information processing speed, a reduction in complaints, and an improvement of quality of life.
Chamoun	2017	between-group	Motion and orientation discrimination task.	No effect of pharmacological manipulations of cholinergic neurotransmission on Neurotracker performance compared with a placebo. Young adults improved their Neurotracker performance.
Chermann	2018	within-between-group	SCAT (concussion) and M-BESS (balance)	Athletes have impaired Neurotracker learning rates after injury. Performance was correlated with the number of symptoms, SAC- and M-BESS scores 48 hours after injury.
Corbin-Berrigan	2018	intervention		Individuals with mTBI showed smaller training gains at visit 2 than healthy controls, but the groups did not differ on the remaining visits.
Corbin-Berrigan	2020a	intervention	Balance and Coordination evaluation; Self-reported fatigue; Self-efficacy on athletic skills and mTBI presentation related to physical activity; computerized cognitive test battery	Clinically recovered mTBI patients improved Neurotracker performance with training but there was no transfer to balance, coordination, self-efficacy, fatigue or cognitive efficiency.
Corbin-Berrigan	2020b	intervention	Balance test (BESS), Self-Efficacy, ImPACT, PCSF	Symptomatic children after mTBI can safely perform Neurotracker training. Self-reported fatigue ($p = .05$) and possibly cognitive efficiency ($p = .08$) improved, but there was no change in coordination, balance, self-efficacy or parent-reported quality of life, and no non-Neurotracker comparison group.
Fabri	2017	within-between-group	Postural stability on different surfaces	Older children perform better than younger children in Neurotracker. For both groups, Neurotracker can be combined with a postural stability task without performance impairments.

Faubert	2012	theoretical paper	-	Predicts that Neurotracker training will increase in-field performance in sports, improve collision awareness and that it will be proved useful for concussion assessment.
Faubert	2013	between-group	-	Professional athletes, high-level amateurs, and non-athlete university students significantly differ in Neurotracker learning.
Fragala	2014	intervention (with resistance training)	Visual reaction time (Dynavision D2) and blood parameters (BDNF)	Resistance training might preserve or improve spatial attention and reaction time with aging.
Harenberg	2016	correlation	laparoscopic surgery task	Neurotracker performance correlates positively with simulated laparoscopic surgery performance.
Harris	2020a	between-group and intervention	MOT, n-back task	Undergraduate students show neither near transfer (2D MOT) nor far transfer (route monitoring task) but did improve working memory performance.
Harris	2020b	intervention	MOT, n-back task, concurrent route recall and auditory monitoring task (real-world military task)	Undergraduate students show Neurotracker learning effects and improvements in a working memory transfer task.
Legault	2012	intervention	Biological motion task	Biological motion perception improved with Neurotracker training at 4m viewing distance, but not at 16m.
Legault	2013	between-group and intervention	-	Older adults show slower tracking speeds than younger adults in the 4-target condition and younger adults have overall higher speed thresholds.
Lysenko-Martin	2020	correlation	Diagnostic for post-concussion syndrome (PCS); SCAT (concussion)	Neurotracker performance in under 13 year olds with a concussion history is positively associated with cognition and balance and negatively associated with concussion symptom severity. Males show better Neurotracker performance than females.

Mangine	2014	correlation	game statistics from season; D2 for visual motor reaction time	NBA point guards and shooting guards possess a faster Neurotracker speed threshold than players from other positions. NBA performance (steals, turnovers, assists) is associated with Neurotracker performance.
Michaels	2017	correlation	Driving task	Neurotracker performance is associated with elevated crash risk and with decreased driving speed, particularly among older adults.
Mejane	2019	within-group comparison	jumping task (knee rotation)	Neurotracker has no significant effect on knee rotations, either pre- or post-fatigue. A subgroup of 12 athletes showed a significant increase in knee abduction when tested simultaneously with Neurotracker, only in the fatigued condition.
Moen	2018	intervention	Attention network test; Anti-saccade task; Color-shape-task; Letter memory task.	Athletes from different sports show Neurotracker learning effects but no transfer effects to executive functions.
Musteata	2019	intervention	Verbal Learning Test (Episodic memory), Digit Span (working memory), D-KEFS Trail Making Test (processing speed, motor speed, cognitive flexibility), D-KEFS Verbal Fluency Test (processing speed, cognitive flexibility), Stroop Test (selective attention, psychomotor speed, cognitive flexibility)	Older adults show Neurotracker learning effects and transfer effects to memory and working memory tasks. Positive transfer was also found for cognitive flexibility and processing speed.
Parsons	2016	intervention	IVA+Plus CPT, WAIS-III subtests: symbol; search, code, block design, number sequence, letter-number sequence and spatial span; d2 attention test; D-KEFS	Neurotracker training can improve attention, visual information processing speed, and working memory, and also leads to changes in resting-state neuroelectric brain function.
Plourde	2017	within-between-group		Stereopsis boosts performance on the Neurotracker task in children and adults, but has no impact on older adults' performances.
Romeas	2016	intervention	Soccer field test	Decision-making accuracy in passing, but not in dribbling and shooting of university-level soccer players is improved with Neurotracker training.

Romeas	2019	intervention	Biological motion perception task	Consolidated Neurotracker training (i.e. training with Neurotracker first and the motor or perceptual task thereafter) leads to better Neurotracker performance than simultaneous Neurotracker training when combined with a motor task but not when combined with a perceptual (biological motion perception) task.
Tullo	2018a	correlation	WASI-II	Neurotracker performance is positively associated with fluid reasoning intelligence.
Tullo	2018b	intervention	CPT-3; WASI-II; FSIQ derived from verbal and non-verbal subtests included in the respective Verbal Comprehension Index (VCI) and Perceptual Reasoning Index (PRI).	Neurotracker training improves CPT-3 performance (rapid response to flashed letters, non-response to 'X') in school-age children with neurodevelopmental conditions
Vartanian	2016	intervention	ShIPLEY-2 working memory span tasks	Members of the Canadian Armed Forces show significant gains in working memory span (verbal, visual, and matrix span) after Neurotracker training.

477 *Note.* Studies are sorted in alphabetical order. Please note that the findings reported here are those claimed by the authors. In some cases, as discussed later, the findings are
 478 questioned due to methodological concerns (see Table 5 and the discussion thereafter). Abbreviations: CPT-3 = Conners Continuous Performance Task; D-KEFS = Delis-Kaplan
 479 Executive Functions System Color-Word Interference Test; FSIQ = Full Scale Intelligence Quotient; ImpACT = Immediate Post-Concussion Assessment and Cognitive Testing;
 480 IVA+Plus CPT = Integrated Visual and Auditory Continuous Performance Test; M-BESS = Modified Balance Error Scoring System; mTBI = mild traumatic brain injury; PCSI = Post-
 481 Concussion Symptom Inventory; SCAT (SAC)= Standardized Assessment of Concussion; WAIS = Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale; WASI-II = Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of
 482 Intelligence – Second Edition

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483 Intervention Studies

484 In this section we will evaluate the scientific quality of the intervention studies. As Simons et al.
485 (2016) argued for studies of “brain training” products, the inclusion of appropriate control groups,
486 ideally “active” controls with similar demand characteristics to the treatment group, are critical to
487 understand the training and transfer effects of an intervention. It may not be possible to always
488 follow best practices in a study because of their applied nature (e.g., in the sports context).
489 Nevertheless, including a control group that did *not* train with Neurotracker and adding a transfer
490 task can be seen as the minimum requirement to garner quality evidence regarding whether
491 Neurotracker training improves another skill. Of the 16 intervention studies, 10 studies fulfilled these
492 two criteria while 6 studies did not. In Table 4, we indicate the extent of transfer effects on attention,
493 awareness, executive function, working memory, processing speed (all near transfer), and decision-
494 making (far transfer), first for the 10 studies which fulfilled the two criteria (black font) and
495 thereafter for those that did not (grey font).

496 In the following, we summarize the results of each of these 16 studies and discuss whether
497 certain methodological concerns apply. Simons et al. (2016, p. 171ff.) criticized studies that have
498 small sample sizes, are not preregistered (with an analysis plan including explanations how variables
499 are coded and analyzed), are suggestive of benefits without mentioning negative consequences, omit
500 adequate controls for placebo effects, have passive or active but unmatched control groups
501 (matching control groups is required to “equate for all aspects of the intervention other than the
502 hypothesized critical ingredient, including expectations to the extent possible”), do not have random
503 assignment to conditions, do not fully report and analyze outcome measures, are not independent
504 from other studies, assess benefits only for the trained task or very similar tasks, rather than
505 assessing transfer, rely on secondary analyses that should be treated as exploratory, or report that
506 interventions work by analyzing only a subgroup of participants.

507

Table 4.

508

Intervention studies and their characteristics

Study characteristics				Neurotracker Effects			Type of transfer		Near transfer effects					Far transfer effects
ID	First author	Year	Web	M	L	T	Near	Far	Attention	Awareness	Executive function	Working memory	Processing speed	Decision-Making
1	Tullo	2018	No	█	█	█	█				█			
2	Harris	2020a	No	█	█	█	█	█				█		█
3	Moen	2018	Yes	█	█	█	█				█			
4	Musteata	2019	Yes	█	█	█	█				█	█		
5	Fleddermann	2019	No	█	█	█	█	█	█			█	█	█
6	Legault	2012	Yes	█	█	█	█		█					
7	Vartanian	2016	Yes	█	█	█	█					█		
8	Harris	2020b	No	█	█	█	█					█		
9	Romeas	2016	Yes	█	█	█	█	█						█
10	Parsons	2016	Yes	█	█	█	█		█			█	█	
11	Legault	2013	Yes	█	█	█	█							
12	Romeas	2019	Yes	█	█	█	█							
13	Corbin-Berrigan	2018	No	█	█	█	█							
14	Corbin-Berrigan	2020a	No	█	█	█	█					█	█	█
15	Corbin-Berrigan	2020b	Yes	█	█	█	█					█	█	█
16	Assed	2016	Yes	█	█	█	█					█	█	

509

Note. Studies are sorted by the number of participants in descending order (the same study IDs are used Table 5 and 6). Web – indicates whether the reference is included at Neurotracker.com. Neurotracker effects (M = “Measurement”, L = “Learning”, T = “Transfer”; see Table 2 for definitions), Type of transfer (Near – to a similar task or cognitive domain, Far – to a real-life task) provides a summary of the subsequent columns: trained skills (attention, awareness, decision-making, executive function, working memory, and processing speed). Colors: green = positive effects; yellow = positive effects with methodological concerns; red = no effects; blank = not tested. Studies highlighted with grey text are not counted as intervention studies as they did not include a transfer task (study 11-13) and/or did not include a control group (study 14-16).

515

516 **Table 5**

517 *Neurotracker intervention studies that include transfer tasks and at least one control group (i.e. a group that did not train with Neurotracker).*

Study ID	Intervention group							Control group							Transfer Test
	N	Participant type	Age M or range	Training task	Training time (min)	Intervention interval	Type of control	Matched control	N	Participant type	Age M or range	Training task	Training time (min)	Training interval	
1	43	students with ASD, ADHD, Intellectual disability	13	NT	105	15 sessions over 5 weeks	active, passive	Age, FSIQ, PRI, WASI-II scores	86	students with ASD, ADHD, Intellectual disability	13	Computer game (2048)	105	15 sessions over 5 weeks	
2	63	students	23	NT	90 or 150	3 or 5 sessions	passive	-	21	students	23	-	0	-	EF
3	31	wrestling, handball, biathlon, and alpine skiing	17-35	NT	186	9 - 76 sessions (M=26.5)	passive	age	29	soccer, paralympic sports, boxing orienteering	17-35	-	193	14 - 61 sessions (M=27.5)	WM, DM
4	25	older adults	61-89	NT	420	14 sessions over 7 weeks	passive	education, dementia, memory, age expertise and age	22	older adults	60-90	-	0	-	EF, DM
5	22	volleyball experts	17	volleyball training + NT	384	8 weeks, 2 x 3 sessions each week	active	age	21	volleyball experts	21	volleyball training	384	8 weeks, 2 x 3 sessions each week	EF, WM
6	14	older adults	64-73	NT	150	5 sessions, one each week	active passive	age	27	older adults	64-73	Contrast task	n. d.	5 sessions	A, WM, PS,DM
7	13	Canadian Armed Forces	26-50	NT	100	10 sessions in 2 weeks	active, passive	Demographic & cognitive variables	28	Canadian Armed Forces	21-50	dual n-back task (auditory + visual)	100	10 sessions in 2 weeks	A
8	18	students	23	NT	100	5 sessions	passive	-	18	students	23	-	0	-	WM
9	7	university-level soccer players	22	NT	210	5 weeks, 2 sessions each week	active, passive	-	12	university-level soccer players	22	watch 3D soccer videos	150	5 weeks, 2 sessions each week	DM
10	10	students	24	NT	600	10 sessions; 2 per week, over 5 weeks	passive	age, education	10	students	23	-	0	-	A, WM, PS

518 *Note.* Studies are sorted by the number of participants in descending order. Abbreviations: f = female; FSIQ = Full Scale Intelligence Quotient; mTBI = mild traumatic brain injury; NT =
 519 Neurotracker; PCS = post-concussion syndrome; PRI = Perceptual Reasoning Index; WASI-II = Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence – Second Edition), EF = Executive functions, WM =
 520 Working memory, DM = Decision Making, A = Attention, PS = Processing speed.

521 **Table 6**522 *Neurotracker intervention studies without control groups or with control groups also receiving Neurotracker training and/or studies with no transfer task.*

Study ID	Intervention group								Control group					Transfer	
	N	Participant type	Age M or range	Training task	Training time (min)	Intervention interval	Type of control	Matched control	N	Participant type	Age M or range	Training task	Training time (min)		Control interval
11	20	younger observers	18-35	NT	150	5 sessions (one each week)	active	-	20	older observers	64-73	NT	150	5 sessions	-
12 (Exp.1)	16	badminton athletes;	23	NT + motor task	270	9 sessions	active	-	13	badminton athletes university level	23	isolated MOT or motor task	270	9 sessions	-
12 (Exp.2)	13	non-athletes	23	NT + perceptual task	270	9 sessions	active	-	13	athletes; no mTBI symptoms	21	isolated MOT or perceptual task	270	9 sessions	-
13	13	mTBI patients	14	NT	144	6 sessions	active	-	13	healthy control group of children	13	NT	144	6 sessions	-
14	10	clinically recovered mTBI patients	15	NT	90	6 visits (3 sessions each), one every 3-7 days	active	-	10	healthy control group of children	13	NT	90	6 visits (3 sessions each), one every 3-7 days	WM, PS
15	9	children with PCS	9	NT	126	6 sessions; one every 2-7 days	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WM, PS
16	1	old man	80	NT + WM task	672	32 sessions over 16 weeks	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WM, PS

523 *Note.* Studies are sorted by the number of participants in descending order. Abbreviations: f = female; FSIQ = Full Scale Intelligence Quotient; mTBI = mild traumatic brain injury; NT =
524 Neurotracker; PCS = post-concussion syndrome; PRI = Perceptual Reasoning Index; WASI-II = Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence – Second Edition), WM = Working memory, PS =
525 Processing speed.

526 *Intervention studies meeting the minimum quality criteria*

527 *Study 1.* In children with neurodevelopmental disorder (e.g., with ASD or ADHD), Neurotracker
528 training was found to improve performance withholding of responding when an 'X' was presented
529 but pressing a key when another letter was presented (the CPT-3 Conners Continuous Performance
530 Test) (Tullo, Guy, et al., 2018). 129 participants from elementary and secondary schools were
531 assigned to three groups: a Neurotracker intervention group (Neurotracker), an active control group
532 (computer game) and a passive control group. The training duration was 5 weeks. The groups were
533 matched on age and two WASI (Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence) intelligence sub-scales.
534 The Neurotracker group improved significantly more than the control group (which did not improve
535 at all) in Neurotracker and CPT-3 performance indicating a near-transfer to executive functions.

536 *Study 2.* No transfer effects were found from Neurotracker training to a 2D-MOT task or to a
537 simulated driving task, but improvements were found for a working memory task (Harris, Wilson,
538 Smith, et al., 2020a). 84 participants were randomly assigned to a passive control group or one of
539 three Neurotracker training groups (5 or 3 large screen sessions or 5 small tablet sessions). All groups
540 were tested in near transfer tasks (2D-MOT, working memory) and a far transfer task (a route recall
541 task used in military settings). The results showed significant Neurotracker learning effects in all
542 intervention groups and a marginally significant learning effect in the control group ($p = .051$, $d =$
543 0.45). For the 2D-MOT task, all groups significantly improved performance from pre- to post-test,
544 with no significant difference in amount of improvement. For the working memory task, significant
545 improvements were observed for the full, portable and abbreviated training but not for the control
546 group. There was no time or group effect for the far transfer task. The authors were surprised by not
547 finding a near transfer effect to 2D-MOT and state: "If any transfer effect from Neurotracker training
548 does exist in this case, it is much smaller than the improvement from repeating the MOT test."
549 (Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020, p. 5). A limitation was acknowledged by the authors for the
550 working memory measure. As in their previous study, groups were not well balanced at pre-test, so
551 that, for example, the abbreviated 3 session group was no better than the control group at the post-

552 test. A further limitation is that the driving task has not previously been validated and may not be a
553 fair test of Neurotracker.

554 *Study 3.* Moen et al. (2018) found, for elite athletes in several sports, that Neurotracker training
555 did *not* improve executive function. Four executive function tests were used: an attention network
556 test, anti-saccade task, color shape task and letter memory task. Two groups were compared, one
557 with athletes from wrestling, handball, biathlon, and alpine skiing and one with athletes from soccer,
558 paralympic sports, boxing and orienteering. The authors used a cross-over design so that both groups
559 acted as an intervention and as a passive control group once. After each intervention phase, changes
560 in executive functions were examined. The intervention groups showed no differences compared
561 with the control groups in executive functions. In both intervention phases, the intervention groups
562 improved their Neurotracker performance over time. The authors concluded that Neurotracker may
563 not be appropriate to improve specific executive functions. Note, however, that there was a wide
564 range of training sessions in both groups (between 9 and 76 training sessions in group 1 and between
565 14 and 61 sessions in group 2) and a variable number of targets to track (between 2 and 4). Thus,
566 training duration and tracking difficulty were different between groups, which could have affected
567 the average performance in both groups.

568 *Study 4.* Musteata et al. (2019) found Neurotracker transfer effects in long-delay recognition
569 memory performance, cognitive flexibility and selective attention in older adults. In their study, 25
570 older adults received 14 Neurotracker training sessions over seven weeks. Participants in the
571 intervention and the passive control group ($n = 22$) underwent some cognitive tests (executive
572 functions and working memory; 18 different variables) before as well as one and five weeks after the
573 intervention. One week after training, the intervention but not the control group showed
574 improvements in working memory ($p = .01$, partial eta squared=.138; California Verbal Learning Test
575 Second Edition) and executive functions (i.e., category switching, $p = .050$, partial eta squared=.083).
576 Improvement in the Stroop inhibition task ($p = .050$, Partial Eta Squared =.082) was reported, but this
577 effect was only found in the "OFF" version of the task (i.e., when the examinees name the color of

578 the ink of a set of number signs). The two claimed " $p = .050$ " results seem, however, to reflect
579 erroneous statistical reporting. The p value for the OFF Stroop test was reported as .050, the F -
580 statistic reported in the associated table, 4.002, seems to instead correspond to $p=.056$. The F
581 statistic reported in the text, as opposed to the table, is different (4.065), which corresponds to
582 $p=.055$, assuming that the denominator degrees of freedom given (25) were correct and the
583 numerator is 1 as it is a simple contrast. And for the executive function test reported as $F(25) = 4.065$,
584 $p = .050$, instead $F(1,25) = 4.065$ corresponds to $p=.055$. Additionally, correction for multiple
585 comparisons would have been in order as there were 18 cognitive sub-tests investigated. Five weeks
586 after the intervention, none of these group differences were statistically significant anymore.
587 Instead, other effects (e.g., episodic memory) were observed and it was explained that Neurotracker
588 training could lead to some "delayed effects". Based on the episodic memory effect 5 weeks after
589 training, the authors state that Neurotracker intervention "[...] may play a significant role in dementia
590 prevention or cognitive decline but further research is needed to ensure reliability and validity"
591 (Musteata et al., 2019, p. 12). A strength of this study is that all cognitive variables were comparable
592 at pre-test for the two groups. At least two of the reported statistics were apparently not reported
593 correctly, however. The study results suggest that, even if there are working memory and executive
594 function effects, they are no longer visible 5 weeks after an intervention. Since it was not controlled
595 what participants did after the intervention, the effects observed 5 weeks post-intervention should
596 be interpreted more cautiously.

597 *Study 5* Neurotracker seems to lead to improvements in processing speed and sustained
598 attention in volleyball experts, without significant working memory improvements or far transfer
599 effects (Fleddermann et al., 2019). The intervention group received 8 weeks of Neurotracker training
600 with 2 sessions per week and was compared to a control group that received only regular volleyball
601 training. Neurotracker performance, memory span, working speed, sustained attention and
602 processing speed were compared between groups. A far-transfer task of physically jumping (block
603 jumps) under single and dual-task conditions was included. The "dual-task high" block jump condition

604 may potentially mirror some of the demands of Neurotracker because the participants had to
605 monitor the movements of a (video-recorded) attacking player with their peripheral vision and
606 perform a maximum block action to the right or left depending on the movement direction of the
607 attacking player. The Neurotracker group improved their Neurotracker performance, in contrast to
608 the control group. The Neurotracker group also showed improvements in sustained attention and
609 processing speed (near transfer). In the far transfer task, response accuracy was over 95% for pre-
610 and posttest in both groups and the main dependent measure, jumping height, showed no
611 differences between groups (Fleddermann et al., 2019, p. 1599). Study strengths are its fairly large
612 sample size of high-level athletes, including a control group, although the intervention group likely
613 had a greater expectation of improvement.

614 *Study 6.* Results from Legault and Faubert (2012) suggest a transfer effect of Neurotracker
615 training to biological motion perception in older adults. A Neurotracker group trained on
616 Neurotracker in five 30-minute sessions while for a control group, the five sessions consisted of
617 training on recognizing the orientation of a simple stimulus at progressively (controlled by a
618 staircase) lower contrast. After the last session, both groups were tested in a task to discriminate the
619 motion direction of a point-light figure, which was masked by noise dots. The dependent variable
620 was the tolerable noise quantity (the more the better). After the training, more noise dots could be
621 tolerated by the Neurotracker group compared with the control group but only for one of the two
622 simulated viewing distances ($p = 0.04$). The control group did not become better in the contrast task
623 over the course of training. Comparing an intervention to an active and passive control group is one
624 of the strengths of the study. The choice of the control task, however, seems not to be a fair
625 comparison to the intervention group, because Neurotracker training improves the tracking of
626 targets amidst distractors, a skill which is also needed in the transfer task, where the noise dots were
627 distractors. Thus, the kind of transfer is difficult to classify here. The contrast task did not involve
628 motion perception or demand sustained attention. Also, the authors did not provide information on

629 performance in the pre-test, so it remains unclear whether the Neurotracker group improved more
630 on the motion task.

631 *Study 7.* Working memory performance improved in a military population after Neurotracker
632 training (Vartanian et al., 2016). The study assigned members of the Canadian Armed Forces (age 21-
633 50) to an intervention group ($n = 13$), active control ($n = 13$), and passive control ($n = 14$) group. The
634 intervention group received 10 minutes of Neurotracker training 10 times over 2 weeks. The active
635 control group was trained in a working memory task: an adaptive dual auditory-visual n-back task.
636 The results indicate that Neurotracker performance improved with training. The Neurotracker
637 training group also improved in word span ($p = .005$, $d = .96$), visual span ($p = .050$, $d = .60$) and
638 matrix span ($p = .015$, $d = .79$) while for the active control group the improvements did not reach
639 statistical significance: word span ($p = .056$, $d = .56$), visual span ($p = .057$, $d = .58$) and matrix span (p
640 $= .180$, $d = .39$). The passive control group showed a trend for improvements in visual span ($p = .198$,
641 $d = .45$) and matrix span ($p = .115$, $d = .49$). While similar improvements for visual span were
642 observed in the active control group and Neurotracker group, verbal and visuospatial working
643 memory capacity improved statistically significantly only in the Neurotracker group. To show a
644 training benefit relative to the control group, however, improvements in training group must be
645 compared directly to the improvements in the control group, which was not reported. A direct
646 statistical comparison of the improvements between those two groups is unlikely to have been
647 significant.

648 *Study 8.* Neurotracker training may improve working memory in university students (Harris,
649 Wilson, Crowe, & Vine, 2020b). In Experiment 2 of this study, 36 participants (no specific sports
650 expertise mentioned) were randomly assigned to a Neurotracker intervention or a passive control
651 group. The intervention group received five sessions of Neurotracker training. Both groups were
652 tested in a pre- and post-test in 2D-MOT and a working memory task (n-back task). The Neurotracker
653 group improved their Neurotracker performance more than did the control group. These
654 improvements did not transfer to advantages in the 2D-MOT task, where performance and gaze

655 behavior during the post-test was not different between groups. The Neurotracker group improved
656 their Neurotracker and working memory performance from pre- to post-test. The improved working
657 memory performance was, however, not different to the control group in the post-test. The authors
658 explain in their limitation section that the groups were not equivalent in working memory
659 performance before training and even the control group had a trend for improvement in working
660 memory performance ($p = 0.08$, $d = .443$, $BF10 = 1.03$). The comparison of performance in the 2D
661 MOT and Neurotracker has to be interpreted with caution, as objects moved on straight paths in the
662 former and random motion paths in the latter. Randomly moving objects are probably more difficult
663 to track. Nevertheless, one might expect that performance might transfer from a more difficult
664 tracking task (Neurotracker) to the likely easier task (2D-MOT).

665 *Study 9.* Neurotracker training could potentially lead to improved decision-making in passing
666 accuracy in soccer (Romeas et al., 2016). The intervention group ($n = 7$) consisted of university-level
667 soccer players who received 10 Neurotracker training sessions (two per week). Data of an active
668 control group ($n = 7$; watched 3D soccer videos in 10 sessions) and a passive control group ($n = 7$)
669 were collapsed in the analyses ($n = 12$; two participants were excluded due to injuries). In a field test,
670 all participants from all groups were randomly distributed to teams and played 5 x 5 soccer matches
671 on a 30m x 40m interior turf soccer field. Decision making accuracy of passing, dribbling and shooting
672 was analyzed with “standardized coding criteria” by one experienced soccer coach (“objective
673 decision-making assessment”), who was blinded to the experimental protocol. Also, subjective
674 ratings of the players’ decision-making (rated from 0% to 100%) were collected at pre and post-test
675 (“subjective decision-making assessment”). The coach’s assessment indicated improved decision-
676 making accuracy in passing (+15%), but not for dribbling and shooting, when comparing Neurotracker
677 with the control group. The subjective confidence ratings were higher in Neurotracker compared
678 with the control group. Rating by a single coach, however, has limited validity. Typical sports training
679 studies using such assessments typically have at least two raters and assess inter-rater reliability (see,
680 e.g., Roca et al., 2013). In general, there was no theoretical prediction that decision-making in one or

681 all of the soccer skills would be improved. That there was no effect for dribbling and shooting could
682 simply be explained by the low number of passes and shots that were observed (this point is also
683 made by the authors). It could be the case that attentional mechanisms (e.g., the monitoring of
684 multiple players) is improved after Neurotracker training. Such a monitoring, however, is not only
685 required for passing but also for dribbling (to avoid another player from taking the ball).
686 Recommending this “training effect” to soccer coaches seems inadequate with the explained
687 limitations. A replication of these effects in a study with a larger sample size, more objective
688 assessments, and a fair control task should be presented first – the choice to collapse the passive and
689 active control groups was questionable. It was not reported whether the results would have been
690 significant without this post-hoc decision.

691 *Intervention studies not meeting the minimum quality criteria*

692 The following studies are meant to be intervention studies but either have no control group at
693 all, a control group that also received Neurotracker training, and/or no transfer test (see Table 4).
694 Thus, they cannot provide evidence for any transfer, but they will be summarized here to provide a
695 complete overview of the literature.

696 *Study 10.* Ten sessions of Neurotracker training might improve attention, visual information
697 processing speed, and working memory and seems to change resting-state neuroelectric activity
698 (Parsons et al., 2014). In this study, 10 university students underwent Neurotracker training over 5
699 weeks and another 10 students acted as a passive control group. Before and after the training, the
700 authors administered 13 cognitive tests thought to be related to selective attention, divided
701 attention, inhibition, short-term memory, working memory, and/or information processing speed.
702 This is the only intervention study included in this review for which the significance level was set to
703 .01. This decision was not preregistered and multiple improvements in the control group yielded p
704 values just above .01. Therefore, to provide information more comparable to the other studies
705 reviewed, we provide an overview of effects statistically significant in the intervention group but not
706 in the control group if the significance level were set to .05 (see Table 6). The two groups were not

707 well balanced for the cognitive variables and even in cases of statistically significant differences, they
708 sometimes show similar scores in the post-test. For example, in the d2 test of attention (working
709 memory), the training group had much lower pre-test scores than the control group (438 vs. 465) and
710 both groups have similar values in the post-test (498 vs. 509). Due to these pre-test differences, only
711 the improvements in the intervention group become significant. A similar concern is evident for the
712 D-KEFS inhibition scores, where both groups have similar values in pre- (43.8 vs. 44.10) and post-test
713 (38.4 vs. 40.2) and for D-KEFS Color Naming, where the control group began with lower values in pre-
714 test (27.3 vs. 24.9) and the two groups have similar values after post-test (23.6 vs. 24.4). Instead of t-
715 tests, a better approach might be an ANCOVA, treating pre-test as a covariate and post-test as the
716 DV, as it would take into account the between-group pre-test differences. It should also be noted
717 that, again, there was no correction for multiple comparisons for the 13 paired t-tests for the pre and
718 post test. Another methodological concern is the possibility of ceiling effects in the “IVA+Plus”
719 scores. When considering tasks without these methodological concerns, only an improvement in
720 working memory remains.

721 The authors also present some EEG results indicating a decrease in 2 to 11 Hz slow-wave activity
722 and a relative increase in beta waves which is interpreted as “attention benefits”. This interpretation
723 is based on EEG studies with clinical trials and patients populations. Whether these findings for
724 patients are transferrable to healthy students could be questioned. This study unfortunately uses
725 unwarranted terms like “cognitive enhancer” to describe Neurotracker, which is not really
726 appropriate given the limitations of the study.

727 *Study 11.* Legault et al. (2013) found that Neurotracker performance in young and old adults
728 increases with practice. In this study, 20 younger adults (18-35 years old) and 20 older adults (64-73
729 years old) received 5 Neurotracker sessions (one every week). Both groups improved, but transfer
730 was not assessed. Younger adults had higher speed thresholds (when tracking three and four targets)
731 than older adults. Unfortunately the paper does not mention whether any participants in the older
732 adults group participated also in the study by Legault and Faubert (2012). The age range was

733 reported to be between 64 and 73 years for both studies, and no note about participants'
734 Neurotracker experience is in either paper, so it is unclear whether the same participants took part in
735 the study or that the same data was used in both studies (compare characteristics of older adults in
736 study 6 – Table 5 with the group of older adults in study 11 – Table 6).

737 *Study 12.* Consolidated Neurotracker training (i.e. Neurotracker training that is finished before
738 another training task begins) seems to affect decision-making in a motor but not in a perceptual dual-
739 task (Romeas et al., 2019). In two experiments, the costs of performing two tasks simultaneously
740 were assessed when Neurotracker was combined with a motor task (Experiment 1) or a perceptual
741 task (Experiment 2). In Experiment 1, 29 university badminton athletes were randomly assigned to
742 four groups: group 1: simultaneous Neurotracker + motor task; group 2: consolidated Neurotracker +
743 delayed motor task; group 3: isolated Neurotracker; group 4: isolated motor task. The motor task
744 was a “birdie interception task” which required participants to intercept a virtual birdie with a
745 badminton racket. The results indicated that Neurotracker performance (speed-thresholds) is
746 impaired in dual-task situations in all groups but that all groups are able to improve single and dual-
747 task performance with training. After the last training session, the highest scores were observed for
748 group 2 (consolidated Neurotracker). In Experiment 2, 26 young adults (non-athletes) were randomly
749 allocated to the same four groups as in Experiment 1. This time the secondary task was a biological-
750 motion perception task, as also used by Legault et al. (2013). This task requires judgement of the
751 walking direction (right or left) of a point-light walker positioned at a (virtual) distance of 4m from
752 the observer. Again, single- and dual-task performance improved with training. This time, there was
753 no advantage of the consolidation group over the other groups. To control for potential sports
754 expertise effects between the two experiments, 16 university level athletes received dual-task
755 training with Neurotracker and the perceptual task. This athlete group and the non-athlete group
756 from Experiment 2 showed no differences in performance. This study suggests that the addition of a
757 motor task leads to greater interference with the Neurotracker as compared to a secondary
758 perceptual task. Nevertheless, the results should be interpreted with caution as a) the groups in

759 Experiment 1 and 2 included only between 5 and 8 participants, b) there were speed-accuracy
760 tradeoffs in the perceptual task in Experiment 2, and c) there were ceiling effects in response
761 accuracy for the perceptual task. Also unfortunate is that although the study did not investigate any
762 transfer effects, specific implementations for training (to combine sport-specific tasks with
763 Neurotracker) are suggested. The authors conclude that “[...] this study provides important insights
764 into optimal training regimens” (Romeas et al., 2019, p. 944). This recommendation seems
765 inappropriate as studies investigating potential transfer effects from dual-task training should be
766 conducted first.

767 *Study 13.* Patients with a concussion history (mTBI) had similar gains after Neurotracker practice
768 as healthy controls (Corbin-Berrigan et al., 2018). Two groups, an mTBI group (mean age: 16) and a
769 healthy control group (mean age: 13), practiced Neurotracker for 6 sessions. Both groups improved
770 but the control group showed higher training gains at session 2. The authors mention study
771 limitations like sample size, age differences and a variable time since the occurrence of the injury.
772 What is also noteworthy is that there were no between-group differences for absolute speed
773 thresholds but only for normalized speed thresholds. Since normalized speed-thresholds have not
774 always been reported in Neurotracker studies, a comparison between studies becomes very difficult;
775 a point that we will discuss later.

776 *Study 14.* Like study 13, this study found that Neurotracker performance improved with practice
777 in children with mTBI history as well as for a control population, with no significant changes in clinical
778 measures (Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020a). Ten participants in each, the intervention and
779 control group, practiced Neurotracker in six sessions (visits every 3 to 7 days). A clinical test battery
780 called ImpACT to assess balance, coordination, self-efficacy, fatigue, and memory was used. The
781 ImpACT consists of 6 subscales: symptom checklist, verbal memory, visual memory, reaction time,
782 processing speed, and impulse control (Corbin-Berrigan, Faubert, & Gagnon, 2020). While both
783 groups improved their Neurotracker performance over time by a similar amount, the clinical
784 measures did not improve significantly for either group.

785 *Study 15.* Corbin-Berrigan, Faubert, and Gagnon (2020b) found no evidence for near transfer to
786 cognitive and motor tasks for mTBI patients performing Neurotracker training. In their study, children
787 with PCS had 6 sessions of Neurotracker practice. In every session, participants' PCS symptoms were
788 checked and cognitive efficiency (ImPACT; includes tests for verbal memory, visual memory, reaction
789 time, processing speed, and impulse control) as well as balance control was tested, and quality of life
790 was assessed with a questionnaire (PedsQL). Participants improved their Neurotracker performance,
791 although looking at improvements between single sessions, participants only improved their
792 performance from visit 3 to visit 4, which is also the time when symptom reductions were observed.
793 In terms of transfer effects, there was no significant improvement in cognitive efficiency ($p = .08$, $d =$
794 1.37) or balance control ($p = .11$, $d = .5$). The only significant improvements were observed in "self-
795 reported multidimensional fatigue" from the quality of life questionnaire. Methodological concerns
796 include: absence of a control group and no correction for multiple comparisons for the 13 paired t-
797 tests for the first and last visit. Moreover, participants underwent active rehabilitation in parallel
798 which might have contributed to the results.

799 *Study 16.* Assed et al. (2016) conducted a single-case study with an 80 year-old man with
800 dementia. He received Neurotracker and memory training in 32 sessions (two weekly sessions of 90
801 minutes each). Working memory training consisted of "verbal and visual mnemonic methods",
802 requiring to remember specific contents. Improvements that occurred for tracking one, two and
803 three targets were claimed, although no statistical tests (or even error bars) were reported. Results
804 indicate that training resulted in a near transfer, i.e., improved working memory performance
805 (accuracy and speed), which was tested with a "computerized memory test" not used in training.
806 Such improvements should, however, be interpreted cautiously, because it was a combination of
807 memory and Neurotracker training and there was only one participant and no control group.
808 Therefore, the results could be due to a placebo effect (Simons et al., 2016).

809 *Summary of intervention study results*

810 For the 16 published intervention studies, it was consistently found that people (athletes,
811 students, healthy young and old adults, military, children with mTBI, children with
812 neurodevelopmental disorders) improve their Neurotracker performance with practice. When it
813 comes to transfer effects, however, any benefits of Neurotracker training are not yet clear (see Table
814 4).

815 Only three intervention studies investigated tasks designed to assess far transfer to real-world
816 demands (see Table 4, "Far transfer effects"). Two of them found that Neurotracker training did *not*
817 improve performance, one in a volleyball-specific task (Fleddermann et al., 2019) and one in a driving
818 task (Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020). Neither of these studies are included in the Neurotracker
819 homepage. The only study cited there found that Neurotracker training improves passing decision
820 making in soccer (Romeas et al., 2016). As explained earlier, however, this finding needs to be
821 replicated with a larger sample, more objective assessments, and a theoretical account of why
822 Neurotracker practice is expected to improve passing accuracy specifically (rather than other
823 football-specific skills).

824 When looking at studies aiming at near transfer effects, six studies are not relevant because
825 they had no control group or no transfer test (Table 4, grey font). From the 10 studies that do
826 provide evidence, nine assessed near-transfer effects, and eight found at least one positive near-
827 transfer effect, but four of those had serious methodological limitations.

828 The only task type for which all near-transfer assessments found a benefit was attention. More
829 specifically, Legault and Faubert (2012) found that the capacity to process biological motion
830 improved, Parsons et al. (2014) and Fledderman et al. (2019) found an improvement in responding
831 selectively to particular letters or digits. None of the studies were preregistered, however, and the
832 first two had some additional methodological concerns (see evaluation of single studies above).

833 The most commonly-assessed transfer effect was working memory. From the six studies on this
834 attentional skill, five found a positive effect of Neurotracker practice, but none were preregistered,
835 three had additional methodological issues, and one study showed no effect.

836 A positive transfer effect was reported for connecting numbers on paper in order with a pencil
837 in athletes (Fleddermann et al., 2019). Clear beneficial Neurotracker transfer effects for executive
838 functions (here: inhibition) have only been found in one study (Tullo, Guy, et al., 2018). There was no
839 transfer effect of Neurotracker training on any of the executive-function tests of the Delis-Kaplan
840 Executive Function System (D-KEFS) in older adults (Musteata et al., 2019). Overall, whether
841 Neurotracker training improves attentional skills is unclear because there are a number of
842 methodological concerns in intervention studies investigating near-transfer effects as well as null
843 results and possible publication bias.

844 According to the Neurotracker website, Neurotracker training improves awareness, but no
845 published study appears to have investigated whether Neurotracker training might improve
846 awareness or perception.

847 It should be noted that even studies examining similar populations with the same methods
848 could either not replicate their working memory transfer effects in a second study in student
849 populations (Harris, Wilson, Crowe, & Vine, 2020; Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020) or find any
850 effect in in patients with a concussion history (Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020; Corbin-
851 Berrigan, Faubert, & Gagnon, 2020). This adds to the concern that the best evidence (best because
852 the study included an active and passive control group) for a working-memory transfer effect, found
853 in military populations with 10 sessions of Neurotracker training (Vartanian et al., 2016), may not
854 replicate.

855 **Overall Summary I: Critical Remarks on the Methods of Neurotracker Studies**

856 In this section, we will summarize some methodological concerns in Neurotracker papers and
857 relate them, if possible, to existing MOT research, to explain the impact of these issues on results.
858 We hope that this list will lead to improved methodology in future Neurotracker research.

859 1) For the statistical analyses, p -values should use the standard .05 threshold (or fully explain
860 and preregister why they use a different standard) and be corrected in case of multiple post-hoc
861 pairwise comparisons. The standardization issue was a problem in the study by Parsons et al. (2014)
862 where p -values were only reported as being significant with $p < .01$. This can evoke suspicion that
863 this threshold was chosen to conceal the many effects found for the control group with $p < .05$ but
864 larger than $p < .01$. The issue of the failure to address multiple comparisons was observed in a
865 number of studies (Corbin-Berrigan, Faubert, & Gagnon, 2020; Musteata et al., 2019; Parsons et al.,
866 2014). These studies had a large number of post-hoc comparisons with p -values being close to .05.
867 These “effects” would have probably not been statistically significant, if the p -values had been
868 corrected for multiple comparisons.

869 2) Studies must be preregistered for readers to have confidence in the p -values associated with
870 the statistical tests, as they may otherwise be diluted by practices including p -hacking, change of
871 analysis strategies (e.g., Romeas et al., 2016), and optional stopping rather than a priori planned
872 sample sizes (Nosek et al. 2018). For example, not committing to a specific sample size or stopping
873 rule when beginning a study can inflate effect sizes or create significant effects that are spurious
874 (Simmons et al. 2011). Unfortunately, none of the Neurotracker studies appear to have been
875 preregistered.

876 3) Many studies describe significant improvements within the training group, but neglect
877 reporting differential improvements (Legault & Faubert, 2012) or rely on an omnibus interaction test
878 without contrasting an individual group with the control group (Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020). A
879 difference in significance between the training and control group (i.e, one is $<.05$ and the other is
880 not) is not the same as a significant difference in the *extent* of improvement. Unless the study
881 showed that the improvement on the transfer task in the Neurotracker group was significantly

882 greater than the improvement in the control group, it did not provide evidence for transfer of
883 training. Besides interaction tests, another approach is that of Tullo, Guy, et al. (2018), who used pre-
884 post differences in inhibition skills as their dependent variable.

885 4) It is not clear whether participants from one study also took part in another study. As an
886 example, the studies by Legault and Faubert (2012) and Legault et al. (2013) both used older adults
887 and reported the same age range (64-73 years old). It was not mentioned whether any of the
888 participants had experience with Neurotracker. Similarly, Faubert and Sidebottom (2012) and
889 Faubert (2013) both report data from an English Premier Team club, a hockey team from the
890 National Hockey League, and a rugby team from the European Rugby. Again, there is no indication
891 whether the same athletes were in both data sets.

892 5) A variety of stimulus characteristics have been used in Neurotracker studies. In some studies
893 the objects bounce off the walls and also change direction when they are close to other objects
894 (Legault et al., 2013; Legault & Faubert, 2012; Romeas et al., 2016). In another study, objects only
895 bounce off the walls but not off other objects (Harris, Wilson, Crowe, & Vine, 2020) and in other
896 studies, it is not mentioned how objects interact (Assed et al., 2016; Moen et al., 2018; Vartanian et
897 al., 2016). This is an important issue as previous MOT research has shown that object distances and
898 interactions affect attentional (Iordanescu et al., 2009; Shim et al., 2008) and perceptual strategies
899 (Vater et al., 2017b; Zelinsky & Todor, 2010) as well as tracking performance (Holcombe et al., 2014;
900 Vater et al., 2017b). Related to this issue, objects randomly changed direction at times in some
901 Neurotracker studies (Moen et al., 2018; Tullo, Faubert, & Bertone, 2018; Tullo, Guy, et al., 2018) but
902 remained on straight paths in others (Musteata et al., 2019; Romeas et al., 2016). Objects with
903 random motion trajectories can be more difficult to track and require a greater amount of sustained
904 attention, although this may be less true when there are more objects to track, because participants
905 then seem to have less knowledge of object velocity (Horowitz & Cohen, 2010; Howe & Holcombe,
906 2012; Luu & Howe, 2015).

907 6) The number of targets to track varied between studies. While most studies used 4 targets and
908 4 distractors, in others only 3 out of 8 objects needed to be tracked (Fabri et al., 2017; Mejane et al.,
909 2019; Plourde et al., 2017; Tullo, Guy, et al., 2018) and others used multiple conditions (e.g., Assed
910 et al., 2016; Moen et al., 2018; Tullo, Faubert, & Bertone, 2018; Tullo, Guy, et al., 2018). The more
911 targets have to be tracked, the more difficult the task (Meyerhoff et al., 2017; Pylyshyn & Storm,
912 1988) and more distractors may mean tracking performance is more affected by suppression ability
913 or by skills specific to target-distractor interactions. These differences also presumably impact on the
914 absolute and normalized speed thresholds and complicate a comparison between studies. One
915 possibility, for example, is that with more targets, visual short-term memory capacity and skill at
916 switching attention among targets are both more critical to performance (Lovett et al., 2019).

917 7) Different dependent variables were used. Some studies used absolute speed thresholds
918 (Corbin-Berrigan, Faubert, & Gagnon, 2020; Fleddermann et al., 2019) while others used normalized
919 speed thresholds (Corbin-Berrigan et al., 2018), and others reported the average speed at which
920 participants successfully tracked three target spheres (Tullo, Faubert, & Bertone, 2018; Tullo, Guy, et
921 al., 2018), the absolute speed gain (Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020), or the number of correct
922 responses (Fabri et al., 2017). To better compare results across studies, normalized speed thresholds
923 may best capture improvement differences between groups, because pre-test values are taken as
924 the baseline.

925 8) Standardization of, or at least detailed reporting of, display sizes and object spacing. Different
926 Neurotracker studies used images projected on multiple walls of a room with shutter glasses to
927 create 3D spheres (Legault et al., 2013; Legault & Faubert, 2012), a single screen with 3D glasses (e.g.
928 Lysenko-Martin et al., 2020; Vartanian et al., 2016) head-mounted displays (Romeas et al., 2016;
929 Tullo, Faubert, & Bertone, 2018), and tablet devices (Chermann et al., 2018; Harris, Wilson, Smith, et
930 al., 2020). Not all of the studies mention the size of the visual field, which is unfortunate because the
931 distance into the periphery of the objects has a very large effect on acuity (Strasburger et al., 2011),
932 causing perceptual demands to vary, potentially dramatically. Most studies that do mention the size

933 indicate it to be between 42° and 48° visual angle (e.g., Chermann et al., 2018; Faubert, 2013;
934 Fleddermann et al., 2019; Harris, Wilson, Crowe, & Vine, 2020; Legault & Faubert, 2012; Mangine et
935 al., 2014; Romeas et al., 2019).

936 Even when the maximum distance into the periphery of the objects is equated, the spacing of
937 the objects has a substantial effect on tracking performance, and on which processes limit
938 performance (Intriligator & Cavanagh, 2001). Denser spacing results in both greater attentional
939 demands and a greater effect of perceptual constraints (Holcombe et al., 2014; Tombu & Seiffert,
940 2011), and the “crowding” perceptual constraint is known to differ substantially across participants
941 (Greenwood et al., 2017) and training may change it significantly (Bertoni et al., 2019). The
942 Neurotracker training studies with different object spacings may, then, be studying the training of
943 different skills.

944 9) Studies used different types of responses to analyze tracking accuracy. Studies varied in
945 whether they required a verbal response (e.g., Musteata et al., 2019; Parsons et al., 2014) or a key or
946 button response (e.g., Moen et al., 2018). It cannot be ruled out that these two response modalities
947 place different demands on working memory, in part because they result in different amounts of
948 total time to indicate all the objects.

949 **Overall Summary II: Factors That Complicate the Comparison of Intervention Studies**

950 Many Neurotracker studies had inadequate control groups and control group tasks. From the 16
951 interventions, only nine included an active control group (three of these included both an active and
952 a passive control group, (Romeas et al., 2016; Tullo, Guy, et al., 2018; Vartanian et al., 2016), five only
953 had a passive control group (Harris, Wilson, Crowe, & Vine, 2020; Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020;
954 Moen et al., 2018; Musteata et al., 2019; Parsons et al., 2014) and two had no control group (Assed
955 et al., 2016; Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020). Unfortunately, some of the control groups had
956 substantially different scores on primary outcomes even prior to the intervention (e.g., Harris,
957 Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020a; 2020b) complicating interpretation.

958 Many intervention studies had small sample sizes, making the results unreliable. Some of the
959 intervention groups consisted of 10 or fewer participants (Assed et al., 2016; Corbin-Berrigan,
960 Kowalski, et al., 2020; 2020; Parsons et al., 2014; Romeas et al., 2016; 2019). The resulting low
961 statistical power means that we cannot know whether contradictory results are due to statistical
962 fluctuations or sometimes-small discrepancies in methods (see Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020
963 and Corbin-Berrigan, Faubert, & Gagnon, 2020).

964 Published studies had a variable amount of training sessions and times between training
965 sessions *within* studies. In some studies, the amount of training sessions is not constant for all
966 participants. In the study by Faubert (2013, p. 3) the observers trained “[...] up to 15 sessions
967 separated over a minimum of five different days [...]”. In a study by Moen et al. (2018), participants
968 had between 9 and 76 training times. The dose-response relation between training and effect is very
969 difficult to discern with such a high variability. Moreover, if one group of participants receives more
970 training than the other, comparing group performance becomes impossible. Another issue is the
971 variable time interval between training sessions. In one study the authors mentioned that there were
972 3 to 7 days between sessions (Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020). While it may not always be
973 possible to guarantee constant intervals between sessions, especially not in clinical populations
974 receiving a treatment or in sports where athletes have a dense training schedule, inter-training
975 intervals should be equated between groups. Providing an explanation for the reason for a training
976 protocol, which typically was not done, is important to make progress on refining or standardizing
977 protocols.

978 Different studies used highly disparate amounts of training, varying from 6 x 3 sessions or
979 approximately 90 minutes of training; (Corbin-Berrigan, Kowalski, et al., 2020; Harris, Wilson, Smith,
980 et al., 2020; Parsons et al., 2014) to 32 x 3 sessions or 672 minutes of training (Assed et al., 2016).
981 Since some studies showed a trend for Neurotracker performance improvement of control groups
982 that received only Neurotracker experience only in test sessions (Harris, Wilson, Crowe, & Vine,
983 2020; Harris, Wilson, Smith, et al., 2020), suggesting that improving Neurotracker performance

984 require little training. The same is true for healthy children and clinically recovered mTBI patients,
985 who both show highest training gains from the first to the second training session (Corbin-Berrigan,
986 Kowalski, et al., 2020). More important is for future studies to focus on what is required to find
987 transfer effects in other tasks.

988 ***Overall Discussion and Suggestions for Future Neurotracker Research***

989 The reviewed studies indicate that some attentional skills like working memory, sustained
990 attention, processing speed or inhibition might improve with Neurotracker training, but the evidence
991 to date is weak. The findings are mixed and could be statistical false positives or the result of greater
992 expectations (placebo effect) in the Neurotracker groups, even relative to some of the active control
993 groups, for which expectations were never measured. There is a large variability not only in study
994 designs but also in Neurotracker stimulus characteristics, experimental setups and statistical
995 analyses.

996 What can sports coaches and players learn from our review? No clear improvements have been
997 found for the all-important transfer of Neurotracker training to actual sports skills. The only positive
998 far-transfer effects found were in a single study, for soccer pass decision making but not other soccer
999 decisions (Romeas et al., 2016). A preregistered replication with improved methods is needed before
1000 one can be confident in the result. In another study, Neurotracker training, in addition to regular
1001 training, did not lead to higher training gains in on-field performance (Fleddermann et al., 2019).
1002 Since practice time is typically valuable, coaches should carefully weigh the pros and cons of using
1003 any training tool. Presently, the evidence for far-transfer is too weak to justify replacing time
1004 available for sport-specific training with Neurotracker training.

1005 What should researchers take into account in future studies? As discussed above, Neurotracker
1006 studies would benefit from being more theoretically driven and precisely targeted, using MOT
1007 research to predict how Neurotracker training might improve attentional skills and guide the choice
1008 of task parameters. Basic studies can assess whether the supposedly-trained cognitive skills are in

1009 fact taxed or “overloaded”. To better combine the results across multiple Neurotracker studies, the
1010 methods (i.e., experimental setup, instructions, responses, analysis) need to be described in full
1011 detail to allow other researchers to replicate findings. Preregistration of study designs and the use of
1012 more appropriate statistics (e.g., corrected post-hoc comparisons) would reduce the concern that the
1013 transfer effects found may be statistical false positives. More confidence in the findings would also
1014 result if researchers shared the (anonymized) data of the studies, as that allows confirmation that
1015 there were no statistical errors (one study of psychology articles found that nearly half made a
1016 particular kind of error Green et al. (2018), and better enables meta-analysis to compare studies
1017 using common statistical methods.

1018 A particular focus of future research should be the attentional skill sometimes known as
1019 “awareness”. No intervention study has yet investigated if awareness can be trained with
1020 Neurotracker. To investigate this in future studies, eye-tracking methods could reveal, whether
1021 strategies such as for the use of peripheral vision develop with Neurotracker training and if these
1022 transfer to real-life tasks, for example, to soccer situations. It comes as a surprise that no published
1023 Neurotracker study has yet used eye-tracking to determine how participants are using peripheral
1024 vision. Participants often are instructed to use peripheral vision to monitor target movements, but it
1025 remains unclear whether they follow these instructions. Since MOT research has found that gaze
1026 strategies can explain performance differences and that stimulus characteristics affect perceptual
1027 strategies (e.g., Fend & Seiffert, 2010; Vater et al., 2017b; Zelinsky & Neider, 2008; Zelinsky & Todor,
1028 2010), it seems mandatory to control for a) eye movements and b) stimulus characteristics. If
1029 peripheral vision usage is indeed linked to better Neurotracker performance, this would be a strong
1030 argument for a prediction that especially game sports could benefit from Neurotracker training,
1031 because peripheral vision is known to be important here (c.f., Vater et al., 2020).

1032 What can the manufacturer take from our review? The main aims of a company typically are to
1033 sell products and potentially access the training data of customers to improve their devices. In
1034 contrast, the customers, for example professional sports clubs, are primarily interested in improving

1035 the performance of their athletes. If the manufacturer shows positive training effects in their
1036 research, sports clubs will likely invest in such training devices, which sounds like a perfect fit
1037 between the two parties. From an objective research perspective, however, promising positive skill
1038 transfer with little or mixed research evidence is not appropriate. Therefore, Neurotracker research
1039 results should be communicated more transparently, with fewer claims that appear to exaggerate or
1040 go beyond the evidence. For example, the Neurotracker's webpage claims that Neurotracker training
1041 helps to "stay sharp under time pressure", "perceptually slow down the environment" or "avoid
1042 overly impulsive action" have not been specifically researched. The Neurotracker webpage reference
1043 list provides a biased picture of the evidence by omitting certain studies with null results.

1044 We agree with the statement of Simons et al. (2016, p. 173) that "If a company claims scientific
1045 proof for the benefits of its products, it must adhere to best scientific practices." Based on the
1046 current status of Neurotracker research, promoting it as a training tool for professional sports or
1047 other domains to improve real-world perceptual-cognitive skills is premature because the far-
1048 transfer effects are up to now either not there or not very solid. Even the claims of near transfer of
1049 Neurotracker training to attentional skills are questionable given the many methodological concerns
1050 in published studies. With our review, we hope to have shown how sport science and basic science
1051 can be better utilized to guide research to assess which skills can be improved with Neurotracker
1052 training.

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1369 **Supplement**1370 **Summary of Non-intervention Studies**

1371 In an observational study, Harenberg et al. (2016, p. 387) expected that Neurotracker
1372 performance would correlate positively with simulated surgical performance because “it requires
1373 attention skills that are important when performing surgery”. In their regression models,
1374 Neurotracker scores were indeed related to surgery skills and explained 29% of the variance for time
1375 to task completion and 28% of the surgical arm movements. Mangine et al. (2014) related basketball-
1376 specific measures of performance to Neurotracker performance (tracking speed and reaction time) in
1377 twelve players. The authors found that tracking speed was strongly associated with statistics from
1378 game play including assists ($r = 0.78; p = 0.003$) and steals ($r = 0.77; p = 0.003$) but there was no
1379 significant relationship with game statistics for a second task of simple visuomotor response time.
1380 The authors conclude that the results reflect the “basketball player’s ability to see and respond to
1381 various stimuli on the basketball court” (Mangine et al., 2014, p. 2406). Note, however, that
1382 correlations based on only twelve participants are expected to be extremely unstable and have very
1383 low statistical power (Schönbrodt & Perugini, 2013). Michaels et al. (2017) compared older and
1384 younger drivers on driving measures (e.g., crash rate, mean speed) and Neurotracker performance.
1385 Lower Neurotracker performance was significantly associated with an elevated crash risk ($r(113) = -$
1386 $.31, p < .001$) and a lower average speed ($r(113) = .47, p < .001$). Because no other basic cognitive or
1387 attentional tasks were used (unless one counts the simple response time task of Mangine et al.
1388 (2014)), it is unclear whether Neurotracker is more correlated with the skills of interest than any other
1389 standardized cognitive or attentional task.

1390 Tullo, Faubert, and Bertone (2018), found that MOT performance positively correlated with
1391 fluid-reasoning intelligence ($r = .41, p = .045$) and that adults with a high fluid reasoning IQ had better
1392 Neurotracker performance. It should be noted that although like other studies it was not
1393 preregistered, it has a relatively high quality as the methods are clearly described, the findings are
1394 related to a number of MOT studies and there is a detailed critical evaluation of study limitations.

1395 Finally, Lysenko-Martin et al. (2020) compared different age groups with and without a history of
1396 concussions. The aim of the study was to test whether 3D-MOT is sensitive to cognition and balance
1397 measures used to diagnose the post-concussion syndrome (PCS). They found that Neurotracker
1398 performance of 104 under 13 year-olds with a history of concussions was not impaired but was very
1399 weakly associated with cognition ($r = .12, p < .001$) and balance ($r = .04, p = .02$). An important note
1400 for this study is that cognitive functioning was better for females than males but that Neurotracker
1401 performance was higher for males than females.

1402 Using a within-between-group design, Chermann et al. (2018) tested healthy rugby players and
1403 rugby players with concussions. The results indicated better performance for healthy players,
1404 improved performance in both groups after training and significantly better Neurotracker
1405 performance in the concussed group at the time they returned to play compared to 48h post-
1406 concussion assessment. Plourde et al. (2017) compared Neurotracker performance with and without
1407 stereoscopic vision (3D glasses) for children, adults and older adults. Neurotracker performance was
1408 best for adults, followed by children and older adults. Performance was better with compared to
1409 without stereoscopic vision in adults and children but not in older adults. A correlation between
1410 scores in a standardized stereoacuity test and Neurotracker scores was not significant for older
1411 adults, suggesting that the two tasks do not measure the same stereoscopic processing (correlations
1412 for the other groups were not possible as they reached the maximum vision acuity scores). In the
1413 third study of this category, Fabri et al. (2017) compared two healthy age groups (5–11 years and 12-
1414 18 years) under single-task (Neurotracker), and dual-task (postural stability task and Neurotracker)
1415 conditions on either a firm or less stable foam surface. The older group showed better Neurotracker
1416 performance than younger participants on both surfaces. In both age groups, postural stability but
1417 not Neurotracker performance was impaired in dual-task situations. As a side note, there were no
1418 differences in Neurotracker performance between male and female participants, in contrast to the
1419 results reported by Lysenko-Martin et al., (2020). Legault et al. (2013) compared Neurotracker speed-

1420 thresholds of younger (22-34 years) and older (61-74 years) participants, and found better
1421 performance for the younger participants.

1422 In a within-group design, Mejane et al. (2019) analyzed knee-joint kinematics in single task
1423 (jumping and landing trials) and dual-task (jumping and landing + Neurotracker) conditions. Between
1424 two sessions, both with single- and dual-task conditions, participants underwent a muscular fatigue
1425 protocol. It was found that the addition of the Neurotracker task had no significant effect on any
1426 knee rotations, either pre- or post-fatigue.

1427 In a between-group design, Faubert (2013) compared Neurotracker learning rates for groups
1428 with different levels of sports expertise for a large sample (n = 308). The paper concluded that
1429 “professionals as a group dramatically differ from high-level amateur athletes, who dramatically
1430 differ from non-athlete university students”. (Faubert, 2013, p. 1153), but no statistical tests were
1431 done. Visual inspection of the learning rate plots suggested that professional athletes started with
1432 higher scores and learned fastest. It is notable that in classic MOT studies, an expert advantage could
1433 not always be shown (e.g., see Schwab & Memmert, 2012).

1434 Chamoun et al. (2017) tested whether a pharmacological manipulation of cholinergic
1435 neurotransmission would enhance complex visual processing in healthy individuals. They compared a
1436 group receiving a medication against Alzheimer’s disease (donepezil) with a group receiving a
1437 placebo (lactose) over 5 weeks. The authors found similar Neurotracker learning effects in both
1438 groups in the final test. Fragala et al. (2014) investigated whether 6 weeks of resistance training in
1439 older adults improves Neurotracker performance. Indeed, the training group performed better than
1440 a passive control group.

1441 Summing these results up, they indicate significant positive relationships between Neurotracker
1442 scores and task performance for a variety of skills, although none of these appear to have been pre-
1443 registered or replicated, so they should be treated with caution. The finding of older participants’
1444 Neurotracker performance being associated with poorer driving performance seems discrepant with

1445 a finding by Bowers et al. (2013) of no relationship with a different MOT task). All of the relationships
1446 were simple correlations from observational studies, such that casual inferences are not warranted.
1447 For example, while the developers of Neurotracker claim that the reasons why expert athletes score
1448 better on Neurotracker than lesser skilled and non-athletes is because it taps into perceptual-
1449 cognitive skills used in competition, it is equally possible that this effect is due to selection (e.g.,
1450 individuals with poorer vision choose not to pursue sports) and/or that higher scores on
1451 Neurotracker are due to general factors (e.g., athletes are more competitive and motivated).

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